

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails
hash://md5/65a3804d52e605937c5568270dd7e63c

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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https://github.com/jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails/issues

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`, has fingerprint `hash://md5/65a3804d52e605937c5568270dd7e63c`, is 444KiB in size and contains 730 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., `parasiteOf`) between 59 primary taxa (e.g., `Escherichia_coli`) and 432 associated taxa (e.g., `Lissachatina_fulica`). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review:

Gippet, J.M.W., Bates, O.K., Moulin, J. et al. The global risk of infectious disease emergence from giant land snail invasion and pet trade. *Parasites Vectors* 16, 363 (2023).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-023-06000-y> https://github.com/jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails
2025-07-12T07:16:39.930Z hash://md5/65a3804d52e605937c5568270dd7e63c

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit https://github.com/jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.10.1
elton	0.15.13
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 444KiB) under review
elton pull jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails

# generate review notes
elton review jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails`, has

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

fingerprint hash://md5/65a3804d52e605937c5568270dd7e63c, is 444KiB in size and contains 730 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., parasiteOf) between 59 primary taxa (e.g., *Escherichia_coli*) and 432 associated taxa (e.g., *Lissachatina fulica*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at [indexed-interactions.html.gz](#) are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Troglostrongylus brevior	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	Gippet, J.M.W., Bates, O.K., Moulin, J. et al. The global risk of infectious disease emergence from giant land snail invasion and pet trade. Parasites Vectors 16, 363 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-023-06000-y . Accessed at https://github.com/jhp oelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnai ls/archive/26bc8 f39ed37574fe8a2c d914fd2a345a46 89034.zip on 17 Jul 2025.

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Strongyloides stercoralis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	Gippet, J.M.W., Bates, O.K., Moulin, J. et al. The global risk of infectious disease emergence from giant land snail invasion and pet trade. Parasites Vectors 16, 363 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-023-06000-y . Accessed at https://github.com/jhp oelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails/archive/26bc8f39ed37574fe8a2cd914fd2a345a4689034.zip on 17 Jul 2025.

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Schistosoma mansoni	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	Gippet, J.M.W., Bates, O.K., Moulin, J. et al. The global risk of infectious disease emergence from giant land snail invasion and pet trade. Parasites Vectors 16, 363 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-023-06000-y . Accessed at https://github.com/jhp oelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnails/archive/26bc8f39ed37574fe8a2cd914fd2a345a4689034.zip on 17 Jul 2025.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rhabditis terricola	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	Gippet, J.M.W., Bates, O.K., Moulin, J. et al. The global risk of infectious disease emergence from giant land snail invasion and pet trade. Parasites Vectors 16, 363 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-023-06000-y . Accessed at https://github.com/jhp oelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandSnai ls/archive/26bc8 f39ed37574fe8a2c d914fd2a345a46 89034.zip on 17 Jul 2025.

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
parasiteOf	730

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Escherichia_coli	103
Angiostrongylus_cantonensis	76
Schistosoma_mansoni	72
Fasciola_gigantica	53
Strongyloides_stercoralis	49
Ancylostoma_caninum	47

sourceTaxonName	count
Pseudomonas_aeruginosa	37
Angiostrongylus_costaricensis	34
Phasmarhabditis_hermaphrodita	27
Aeromonas_hydrophila	27
Klebsiella_pneumoniae	26
Crenosoma_vulpis	25
Aelurostrongylus_abstrusus	20
Angiostrongylus_vasorum	18
Angiostrongylus_malaysiensis	13
Citrobacter_freundii	12
Oslerus_rostratus	12
Acinetobacter_baumannii	10
Cruzia_tentaculata	10

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Lissachatina fulica	40
Canis familiaris	16
Homo sapiens	15
Canis lupus	11
Felis catus	11
Gallus gallus	11
Mus musculus	10
Equus caballus	8
Biomphalaria glabrata	7
Lynx rufus	7
Rattus norvegicus	7
Sus scrofa	7
Oryctolagus cuniculus	6
Culex quinquefasciatus	6
Phoca vitulina	6
Bos taurus	6
Bradybaena similaris	5
Rattus rattus	5
Procyon lotor	5

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Troglostrongylus brevior	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Strongyloides stercoralis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Schistosoma mansoni	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Rhabditis terricola	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Rhabditis axei	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Phasmarhabditis hermaphrodita	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Oslerus rostratus	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Oslerus osleri	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Klebsiella pneumoniae	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Fasciola gigantica	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Escherichia coli	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Cruzia tentaculata	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Crenosoma vulpis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Citrobacter freundii	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Angiostrongylus vasorum	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Angiostrongylus malaysiensis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Angiostrongylus costaricensis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1
Angiostrongylus cantonensis	parasiteOf	Lissachatina fulica	1

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Achatina	SYNONYM_OF	col	Achatina
achatina			achatina
Achatina	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Achatina
achatina			achatina
Acinetobacter	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acinetobacter
baumannii			baumannii
Acinonyx jubatus	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acinonyx jubatus

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	26
col	genus	10
col	species	431
col	subspecies	2
discoverlife	NA	466
discoverlife	species	2
gbif	NA	6
gbif	genus	13
gbif	species	449
gbif	subspecies	2
itis	NA	101
itis	genus	8
itis	species	358
itis	subspecies	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
mdd	NA	468
ncbi	NA	24
ncbi	genus	13
ncbi	species	428
ncbi	subspecies	3
pbdb	NA	214
pbdb	genus	1
pbdb	species	253
tpt	NA	214
tpt	species	254
wfo	NA	468
worms	NA	227
worms	genus	12
worms	species	228
worms	subspecies	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	92
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	446
col	NONE	37
discoverlife	NONE	490
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	1
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	510
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	86
gbif	NONE	8
itis	NONE	115
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	375
itis	SYNONYM_OF	5
mdd	NONE	265
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	226
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	SAME_AS	454
ncbi	NONE	25

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	14
pbdb	NONE	238
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	245
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	10
tpt	NONE	238
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	253
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	1
wfo	NONE	492
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	245
worms	NONE	236
worms	SYNONYM_OF	20

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that

document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2025-07-17T09:45:45Z	summary	https://github.com/jhpoelen/Gippet2023_GiantLandS
2025-07-17T09:45:45Z	summary	730 interaction(s)
2025-07-17T09:45:45Z	summary	0 note(s)
2025-07-17T09:45:45Z	summary	730 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 5: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁵At time of writing (2025-07-17) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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